

The Ndau people of Chimanimani area in Zimbabwe

Data source: Personal Expertise

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** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Religious Group, African Religions, Zimbabwean tribal religion, Language, Afro-Asiatic

The identity of the Ndau people is rooted in the Mnonomotapa Empire before colonization. At the present moment the Ndau people are found both in Zimbabwe and Mozambique. In Zimbabwe Ndau people they occupy the south-eastern parts of the country. In Mozambique, the Ndau are found in areas facing the south-west, and their language is called Ndau. The Ndau people specifically occupy the Chimanimani and Chipinge districts in Zimbabwe. That area was formerly called Gazaland. In the present day, this is largely a rural area which still needs considerable development. They were named the Ndau because they say Ndauwee when welcoming or greeting a visitor into their homestead. This is still their practice in the present day. The term has also a geopolitical dimension. The term Ndau denotes space, and in this regard, the term may raise issues to do with a claim to ownership of their space. The language they speak is also called Ndau. Some people also contend that they were named after their language. Social structures and cultural norms serve to unite and bind together the Ndau people. There has not been much change in the way social and cultural activities are practised. Several of the customs in place in the twentieth century, such as the burial and succession of chiefs, are similar to those practiced centuries earlier. While there has been a few changes with time, the changes have are still applicable and relevant for the present Ndau people. These traditions in Ndau history serve as cultural materials that define aspects of a scripted Ndau identity. Amongst the Ndau people are also special religious specialists who assist the community indigenous knowledge system. Some of the specialists include midwives, n'anga, rain makers and chiefs. These specialists are crucial in preserving both cultural values and the environment. The religious specialists assist the community with the utilization of natural resources responsibly as they strongly believe that the earth or environment is capable of regenerating itself. The Ndau people operate under the influence of a patriarchal social system which upholds the rule and control of men. Men dominate, while women and children are just followers. It is men who hold all decision-making powers, while women and children do not have access to such powers. Women generally do not have a voice to crucial decisions in life. This has resulted in a culture of silence among women in Chimanimani. However the history of these people is highly debatable as there are number of contradictions between narratives from oral tradition and written documents.

Date Range: 1890 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Chimanimani

Region tags: Chimanimani, Southern Africa, Africa, Zimbabwe

The Ndau people of Chimanimani area in Zimbabwe

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hlatywayo, A. and Chirongoma, S., 2023. A Case Study of the Ndaou in Eastern Zimbabwe. Religion and COVID-19 Vaccination in Zimbabwe.
- Source 2: Muyambo, T.M. and Maposa, R.S., 2013. The post-burial rite of Kusemendera Guwa in the indigenous Ndaou culture in Zimbabwe: Insights on enculturation theology. Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies, 4(4), pp.589-593.
- Source 3: Mupangwa, T., 2023. The feminization of poverty: A study of Ndaou women of Muchadziya village in Chimanimani Zimbabwe. HTS Teologiese Studies/Theological Studies, 79(3)

Notes: These sources can also be found on line

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/hts/article/view/245396>
- Source 1 Description: This is a journal article on Ndaou women and how they are tackling and overcoming poverty. It gives a better understanding of this tribe and how women are treated
- Source 2 URL: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/288926304.pdf>
- Source 2 Description: This is a dissertation on Ndaou Indigenous knowledge systems
- Source 3 URL: https://journals.co.za/doi/pdf/10.10520/ejc-linga_v20_n2_a7
- Source 3 Description: It is another journal article that outlines the identity of the Ndaou people and how that identity is under siege

Notes: These were written by people who are insiders of the tribe. They have first hand information about the tribe

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://journals.co.za/doi/pdf/10.10520/ejc-linga_v20_n2_a7
- Source 1 Description: This has some parts of the text in the original language
- Source 2 URL: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Emmanuel-Sithole/publication/335334573_Is_Ndaou_a_Dialect_of_Shona/links/5e7d11dd92851caef4a1f412/Is-Ndaou-a-Dialect-of-Shona.pdf?origin=journalDetail&_tp=eyJwYWdlIjoiam91cm5hbERldGFpbCJ9
- Source 2 Description: It focusses more on the language of the Ndaou people and its origin.
- Source 3 URL: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Emmanuel-Sithole/publication/335334573_Is_Ndaou_a_Dialect_of_Shona/links/5e7d11dd92851caef4a1f412/Is-Ndaou-a-Dialect-of-Shona.pdf?origin=journalDetail&_tp=eyJwYWdlIjoiam91cm5hbERldGFpbCJ9
- Source 3 Description: It describes one of the rituals that is practiced after burial among the Ndaou.

Notes: Most of the written documents are in English and they only have a few quotations in the original language

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: It is because they do not seek to convert other people

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Since they do not seek to convert others to join their religion, the cultural contact which this group establishes with other groups is accommodating, friendly and pluralistic.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: The group does not really feel uncomfortable with other religious groups they interact with in the social space.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: People are not really assigned affiliation but birth makes individuals born into the ethnic group part of the tribe automatically

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: They do not recruit any new members but the tribe or group grows through births within the group

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: It is one of the African traditions that is well established and therefore does not need any official political support

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The belief is that once born a Ndaou you will always be. Therefore there is no way you can reject your identity.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000000

Notes: It is a sizeable area which contributes a sizeable percentage to the country's population

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 5.9

Notes: Although I naturally have significant knowledge about the group but to successfully conduct this research, 60 people were interviewed from the ethnic group.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (not related to larger religious group)

Notes: It is one of the tribal groups that operates independently

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It has religious specialists and most of the time they are the leaders

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Every other leader reports to the chief who is the overall leader of the area

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: The leader is supported by other leaders who are subordinate to him/ her

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: It is one religious community

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):
– Yes
Notes: These leaders who oversee local communities are called Sabhuku (headmen)

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
– Yes
Notes: The overall leader is the chief who oversees the headmen

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
– Yes
Notes: All the headmen form a council of leadership.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
– Number of levels [numeric value]: 3
Notes: The leadership start at family level then goes to village and eventually to the whole district. However these leaders also report the spiritual powers.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
– Yes
Notes: For them to lead well and effectively they need the spiritual powers

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:
– No
Notes: The leadership sometimes runs within a family. Therefore past deeds are not considered at all.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:
– No
Notes: The powers are not acquired by individual deeds because some individuals receive these powers as children. However person endowed with such powers is expected to live an upright life.

↳ Powers are inherited:
– Yes
Notes: The powers can be passed from one generation to another.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: A cultural ceremony is actually held for the powers to be transmitted.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: An individual can go through an apprenticeship from the teacher.

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: Usually the powers are associated with the function the person will perform in the society.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: This is done with the help of spiritual mediums.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

Notes: Usually they choose a person they have a very good knowledge about and have worked with for some time.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

Notes: The leader always work with advisors and are fully involved in the choosing of the new leader.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: Other leaders are always involved as well. They are part of the advisors to the leader.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: Political leaders can be involved in the inauguration of the the leader especially the chief. However this only started recently after the country gained independence. It was strictly a religious event.

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: Other members of the congregation can be involved but it is not always.

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: Usually it is done by a select few (special group) of people not everyone.

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: Spirit mediums are involved in every step of the process.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: They take into consideration the fact that they are human.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Notes: They can pay fine of money, goat, chicken or cow.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: They can be removed from the position of leadership if the error is too grave.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Notes: They can be asked to pay a fine as well of a cow so as not to anger the spiritual powers.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: Especially if they are under the influence of the spirit.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral

scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: They do not have written scriptures however knowledge is passed on orally from one generation to another.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Usually most of the ceremonies are conducted in the homestead, in a round hut which is used as a kitchen. They also use natural resources such as caves, mountains and trees.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: They do not build monumental structures at all

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: They do not use any visual images.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The kitchen, caves, mountains, pools can be considered sacred.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Natural resources are considered to be the abode of spirits.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: There are no pilgrimages because they use the natural resources within their area to perform their rituals.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The spirit will continue to exist when the body dies.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit is the one that can connect with the spiritual realm and the supreme being

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit cannot be seen by physical eye.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The body is the temple of the spirit.

Notes: The spirit needs a body to exist in.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: They believe a person when he or she dies will continue to live in a different realm

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The realm the person will continue to exist seem to be more spiritual than physical.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: However the spirit of a dead person can reside in a living person. It does not happen to everyone.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Certain rituals are performed before and after burial.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: It is not acceptable at all. Cremation is viewed as disrespect to the dead body.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: The body of a dead person is considered sacred, therefore such processes are not allowed.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: They bury the dead in a grave

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Notes: Since the dead body is seen as sacred they are not allowed to do such things. In actual fact if the legs are bent they try to straighten them. They believe that are putting the body in a more comfortable position.

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: The body has to face upwards while lying in a casket.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Notes: The corpse should always be in a lying position.

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Notes: It has to be in a lying position.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: If a person is caught consuming the flesh of another human being, he or she is considered as a witch.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: The corpse is only cleaned and buried in a grave.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: If that is done, it will be considered as disrespect.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: It only happens if the corpse did not receive a proper primary burial.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Notes: The body is only prepared once in preparation for burial.

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Notes: Usually the body is treated using the natural traditional herbs.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There are no sacrifices that are performed during burial.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: They can put beer or food on the grave

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: They put some personal belongings in the coffin which they deem fit should be buried with the corpse.

↳ Valuable items:

– No

Notes: Usually they are given to the relatives who are left behind.

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Nowadays they also put flowers on the grave.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: A well organized burial ceremony is held which has to be attended by many.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: They do not build any monuments for persons buried elsewhere. They actually make an effort to bring the remains of the deceased and do a proper burial which they believe is bringing the spirit of the dead person back home.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Most families have cemeteries for burying their dead.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: They do not practice this however religious leaders such as chiefs are buried in secret places such as secret caves.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: The graves may be close to the homestead but not beneath the house.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Notes: There are no other burial types.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: They believe supernatural beings exist

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: They believe in Mwari Musikavanhu (God the creator) whose intermediaries are spirit mediums

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
– Yes
Notes: He can eat, talk and drink. He can do all what human beings can do.
- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
– No
Notes: He resides in the sacred places such as the caves and mountains
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
– No
Notes: The underworld is considered to be evil.
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
– No
Notes: The king actually gets his powers from the supreme high god.
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– Yes
Notes: The supreme displays his existence through the king. The king is one of the religious leaders.
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
– No
Notes: Usually he has a relationship in terms of what he can do in people's lives not just the elites
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– I don't know
Notes: However the elites are considered leaders, therefore responsibility is expected more from them
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
– Yes
Notes: The supreme being is good though he can punish if one does wrong things
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
– Yes [specify]: He is all powerful, omnipotent, everlasting and all loving
Notes: The characteristics of the supreme high god are similar to those of a Christian

God.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is the creator of the world and therefore is aware of this world

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The supreme being knows everything . He is all knowing.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: His knowledge is not restricted. He knows even the affairs of people outside the sample region.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: He is a universal God therefore knows everyone in the world.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: He created the world therefore his knowledge about the world can not be comprehended by human beings.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god sees you even in the dark, in secret places. Therefore the eye of the supreme being is everywhere

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme being is not restricted by anything. He can see everywhere.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme being knows the intentions of every human being.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme being knows a person's character because he is the one who created the person.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme being uses the spirit mediums to reveal or warn about the future.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Notes: There is a possibility that the supreme being has other knowledge of this world since he is all powerful

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The supreme god gives people free will. Sometimes what happens in the world is a result of people's choices.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The concept of free will also applies. However this does not mean that he can not cause certain things to happen

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Since the supreme is anthropomorphic he can exhibit positive emotion.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: This is usually expressed in the form of a punishment.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: That is why they offer food, drink to the supreme being which they may put on a sacred place or even a grave.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Other supernatural beings can be venerated but not to be worshipped.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

Notes: There are no other features the supreme being possesses besides those mentioned above.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: He communicates through spirit mediums.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Notes: The supreme being communicates on special occasions and incidences.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: It is one way of communication in this religion.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Usually one gets into a trance when possessed by a spirit. This does not happen to everyone.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Diviners are considered religious specialists

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Sometimes the supreme being can cause a child to be sick as a way of communicating through the child.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: Communication can be through anyone

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: misfortunes and sickness

Notes: If a person is no longer appeasing the supreme high god, the supreme god can cause misfortunes in the life of the person as a way of catching his or her attention

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: They are involved in the lives of the living. They are called ancestors

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: A number of people confess to have seen ghosts. Ghosts are spirits of the dead

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Those who are abodes of these spirits can feel physically that the spirit is now upon them.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Because they once lived on this earth

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Because they are not the supreme being.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: They have knowledge even of those outside the sample

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: They have knowledge of people outside the sample region

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Like I mentioned earlier, some of these spirits before they were dead the were relatives of some people outside the sample region. Therefore they have knowledge of people even in other tribes.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: However not restricted only to visible things. Even things done in secret they can see.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: When a person becomes a spirit they graduate to a high level in terms of human existence. Therefore the spirit has more abilities than a physical body.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: They are given the ability by the supreme being.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Notes: They know the character of people they are sent to only. Not everyone in the world

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: People can be warned of pending dangers in life.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

Notes: The knowledge they have is dependent on how much the supreme being has revealed to them.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Their powers are limited.. They can cause something in the world only if they have been given permission by the supreme being.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Their impact is usually felt at individual levels most of the time

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: They can tell you of what once happened before they became spirits.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: If they are pleased they do exhibit positive emotion.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: If they are disappointed by human activity they can exhibit a negative emotion

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: They usually put food, beer on the graves for the spirits to eat and drink

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Notes: They do not possess any other features

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: They can give direction to life

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Notes: They only communicate when there is need to do so

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: But usually they appear in human form in dreams.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Usually the person who is a medium will be in a trance when they communicate.

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: Diviners are part of the religious leaders among this group

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: Even young children can be used to communicate something to a family or the whole group

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: A number of people can be used to communicate including the monarch

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Use of a stranger or someone who is from another tribe

Notes: This usually happens when a person dies and the relatives did not know or was not buried properly in another land outside the family lands

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Notes: There are no non human supernatural beings.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: They do not exist.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: It does not possess a variety of supernatural beings.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Even if you go far away the spirits of the dead will be watching over you

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The community is expected to adhere to certain social norms.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Taboos are to be observed. If not observed the supernatural beings in the form ancestors punish the living

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Certain foods should be eaten during certain special occasions

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: They have to be treated with respect

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: There are sacred objects that are not supposed to be held by anyone except the religious leaders

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Notes: There are no other things they care about.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is not acceptable at all

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: If a group member murders a person even from other tribe they have to appease the spirit of that dead person for his/her spirit will seek revenge if not appeased.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is not tolerated at all

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Notes: They do not care much about sex. It is very rare to hear about them speaking about sex

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Lying is not allowed

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: One has to honor their oaths

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: People are encouraged to work and earn an honest living

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Usually as a wicked source of power.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Fighting in whatever form is not acceptable.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: They encourage doing things during the expected time

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Elders should be respected at all times.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
 - Notes: They are expected to live a harmonious life therefore should avoid anything that may disrupt the peace.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Crime is considered to be unethical in whatever form

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Rituals are to be done as expected culturally.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
 - Notes: They are to be observed and performed as expected culturally.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
 - Notes: There is no proselytization that takes place.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are ways and systems in place to ensure justice in whatever form.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are taboos that help the people to be hygienic all the time.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - No
 - Notes: There are no other things they care for.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: Ancestors usually mete out punishment

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: They do not bestow any rewards

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: They do not have a concept of a savior

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: There is no concept of judgement

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are certain norms and practices that are known and have to be practiced by everyone.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: What is conventionally practiced is considered to be the moral compass for the group. There is no distinction.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Virtues such as patience, kindness, self control are some among many that are advocated for

Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Everyone including the leaders is expected to have these virtues for the community to function well

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: The courage should be based on the fact that the supreme being and ancestors will protect them

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: In life you are expected to have confidence and be able to face challenges fearlessly.

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: It has to be extended to everyone, though emphasis is on the poor, vulnerable and in need.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: There are systems in place to assist with issues of forgiveness especially when families wrong each other.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Especially to the poor though it should be extended to everyone

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: They are encouraged to put other people's needs above theirs.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Notes: everyone is expected to have a morally upright, acceptable and honorable behavior.

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: If not pure you can not participate in certain rituals.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: Respect should be rendered to everyone, though children are expected to respect their

elders.

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: Children are expected to obey their parents

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: It is expected especially in marriage. However women are expected more to be loyal in marriage than men.

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: Especially in community events such as funerals and weddings.

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: They can be creative especially in artistic work

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: Everything has to be done in moderation. They have proverbs relation to being frugal and not overdo things

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: It is one of the virtues expected on everyone

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Notes: Excellence and due diligence is expected in everything.

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Notes: All these are expected though some may not have such qualities.

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: Where there is need to be physically everyone is expected to show the strength, though men are generally believed to be stronger than women physically.

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: However even if you have hold a high status in society you are expected to be humble.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: Pride is disdained . Humility is expected among all.

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: All these virtues are expected to be in a person for they will assist one to make wise decisions.

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Cheerfulness in giving, joy and enthusiasm are expected in every home.

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: Especially in the power and help of the supreme being and ancestors

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: To one another and also to the supreme being and the ancestors.

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: Reverence should be given to the ancestors and the the supreme god

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Total dependence on the supreme being who will help them through the ancestors is required

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: Especially on leaders such as chiefs and kings when solving problems

Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: Everyone should be able to judge well.

Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: Men and women have ways of making themselves attractive. For example ear piercing used to be done by both men and women as a way of edifying beauty.

Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: It is expected from everyone though it is difficult for some to achieve.

Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: There are no other virtues advocated by the group

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Everyone is expected to be married (heterosexual marriages). Celibacy is not a requirement.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Though they encourage abstinence before marriage

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Castration is not required

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is not required at all.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: There are no food taboos to be a Ndau since membership is by birth. As long as your parents are Ndau, you automatically become one.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Membership does not require any markings on the body.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: There are no such requirements

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: It is not acceptable at all.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Child sacrifice is not allowed at all.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Yes

Notes: Suicide is strongly condemned.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: You do not have to give anything to be a Ndau.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: They do not hold any prayer meetings.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: One does not have to take any risk to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: Members are not expected to take an oath though there are some ethical issues to be observed. They have behaviours that are ethically correct which are expected.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: There is no marginalization that is required

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Though they perform rituals at household level, it is not a requirement for membership.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Participation in large scale rituals is not a requirement.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: There are no extra-ritual in-group markers

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: There is no use of fictive kinship terminology.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: It is one of the tribes in Zimbabwe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: It does not provide any institutionalized famine relief. However they can assist one another during famine

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Non governmental organizations provide famine relief to the group.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: It does not because most of them are actually poor and are in need as well.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Non governmental organizations offer poverty relief to the group.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: It does not provide institutionalized care but the elderly and the sick are properly taken care of at family level by women.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: They usually take care the sick and elderly in the home instead of taking them to institutions.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: The group does not have any schools but they acquire formal education in government institutions.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: They attend schools built and run by the government.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: There is no extra religious education offered to the group.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The chiefs, headmen and other religious leaders within the group help in the proper functioning of the group.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The government and non governmental organizations interact a lot with this group.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: It does not provide public food storage. Food is stored at family level.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There is no institution that is offering storage of food for the group.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: It does not provide any water management. The government is responsible with water

management

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The government is responsible with water management in the whole country.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: The government provides transportation infrastructure in the area.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: It is the responsibility of the government through the local government authorities.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: They do not pay any tithes or taxes.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: They do not pay any taxes to any institution.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: The chiefs have a police force which is a traditional one. They assist the chiefs in solving matters in the community.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group interacts with the police force from the government.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: The chiefs and the headmen act as judges.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the matters that cannot be solved in traditional courts are taken to the governmental judicial systems.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Usually the punishment is in the form of a fine

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: Killing is not accepted at all

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: This is very rare and it is only when they see that the person will continue to be a threat to community

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Notes: A person pays a fine of either money, a goat, chicken or a cow, depending with the gravity of the matter.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: This also very rare and when the person is not repentant and is seen as a threat to the community

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: Usually they prefer the person to pay a fine than taking their property.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is for matters that are taken to the governmental court systems

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: The judicial system of the country has that law but it has been a long time since this form of punishment has been performed in the country.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: Most of the time offenders of the law are thrown into prison

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Corporal punishment is part of the punishments

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Notes: A person is thrown into prison instead of ostracism

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: You either pay a fine or serve a sentence

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the legal aspects are not written down . They have been passed from one generation to another.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents are subject to the legal code of the country .

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: They do not have a military force

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the members of the group are in the military force of the country

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The military force of the country protects everyone in the country including the Ndaou people of Chimanimani area

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Their language is not written but it is quite distinct from all other Shona languages in the country.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They learn other languages in learning institutions

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Learning institutions expose the adherents to other languages.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: They follow the calendar the whole country uses

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government provides a calendar to the whole country with school dates, school holidays

and other religious holidays

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Each family has to produce its own food.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Each family has a field where they grow their crops and produce food.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Non governmental organizations and the government's social welfare department sometimes provide food aid during drought years.

Bibliography

General References

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